

WHEN LEADING BECOMES A BURDEN: PHENOMENOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION INTO ACTUAL EXPERIENCES OF STUDENT LEADERS UNDER “LEADERSHIP PRESSURE”

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When Leading becomes a Burden: Phenomenological Investigation into Actual Experiences of Student Leaders under “Leadership Pressure”

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Abstract

Student leaders assume leadership responsibilities in school, in various organizations, or in other settings. These leaders are essential to the development of the school community because they represent and secure the students' general welfare. However, due to responsibilities and pressure, their leadership and academic performance are impacted. The study unveils experiences of student leaders along with how it affects health and determines coping mechanisms to bounce back from leadership pressure. A purposive sampling is used on student leaders at Central Luzon State University, Philippines to identify three subjects for qualitative phenomenological study. Semi-structured interviews were conducted and analyzed thematically. Results revealed that being a leader was somewhat a burden in terms of handling conflicting tasks, dealing with expectations that brought pressure in decision-making, and upholding quality of leadership and academic performance while maintaining quality of life. In spite of that, pressure was bearable through unique ways of coping with pressure like entertaining themselves or seeing products of their hard work. Educational institutions must look deeper into the wellness of student leaders as they are pillars contributing to harmony not just in school premises, but also in the mentality of constituents.

Keywords: *leadership pressure, student-leaders, education, coping mechanisms, leadership experiences*

Introduction

Student leaders have a required skill that puts them in the role. They are the pillar that keeps the school and its fellow students organized. Student leaders create a supportive environment where everyone can learn and progress. One of their roles is to develop and create a school atmosphere where everyone can grow and use their abilities to grow as individuals (Hopkins et al., 2020). The educational institution's goal is to develop students' growth as leaders and maximize their potential, allowing them to thrive (Pedersen et al., 2018). However, they must deal with pressure as the person who sets a model for others to follow.

One strategy to improve student performance and concept retention has been thought to be giving them leadership roles that let them participate in decision-making in their academic endeavors (California State University, 2012; Office of Institutional Research, 2011; cited by Irsheid, 2018). The leader is the heart and soul that keeps an organization alive (Lualhati, 2019). Student leaders must employ their integrity and leadership abilities to fulfill the demands passed upon them and leave an impact on fellow students (Chai, 2015; as cited by Zorina et al., 2018).

Education is crucial to a student's performance in curricular and extracurricular activities. Additionally, it significantly contributes to their personal growth and development (Radhika, 2018). Like education, leadership is a crucial component in achieving the purpose and goal of an organization. Not only the vision of an organization but also the leaders themselves benefit from developing their values and skills that they can utilize in our society in the future (Lim, 2022). It's known that leadership is among the utmost obstacles that our society and agencies must address to attain aims and objectives and consequently achieve long-term and holistic human development (Cáceres-Reche, 2021). In addition, factors that influence academic performance should be identified since they are vital to research in education and in general. With that, it has been found that factors such as stress and motivation are the reasons behind the academic success that individuals experience (Jiménez-Mijangos et al., 2022). Stress is the most stated factor that influences the students' capability to perform academically (Lust et al., 2019). Moreover, identifying and addressing stress and pressure that affect students is vital since it can help institutions and students themselves. Acknowledging the issues students encounter can help them be aware and help themselves resolve these issues to avoid more complex problems that can result from this, which can eventually affect their personal and professional lives in the future (Gustems-Carnicer et al., 2019).

The transactional model of stress and coping, created by Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman in the 1980s, was employed in the study as the theoretical background. It is a well-accepted psychological theory. It is a thorough approach to comprehending how people feel and react to environmental stresses and has been used in many situations, including employment, education, health, and relationships. The idea stresses how people constantly assess and reassess their experiences and resources, which highlights the interactive aspect of stress and coping.

Accordingly, the research goal is to dive deeper into the perspective of student leaders when they experience stressors such as leadership and academic pressure. Knowing the value of student leaders in influencing schools and organizations will enable those who care for and need to make adjustments for their renowned leaders so that they can improve or sustain the things, ideas, and concepts in this study. Further, this study would awaken those communities to what their leaders go through so they can subject themselves to being of help to their leaders.

Research Objectives

Through a phenomenological approach, the study aims (1) to determine the challenges faced by being a leader and (2) to delve deeper into the influence of leadership pressure on their academic performance and mental health and how they deal with it.

Literature Review

Experiences of a student leader

Leadership is not for everyone. It is a skill that requires the understanding and performance of various concepts, ideas, and qualifications (Gurr et al., 2020). Leadership is a crucial skill that could imply the unity of a group, how they handle success and failure, and how they respond to the leader (Swanson et al., 2020). A good leader in business unites the workers by upholding the values that earlier leaders suggested (Ciulla, 2020). In politics, the wise leader keeps a community together by sensibly using the power at their disposal to uphold justice and order (Magstadt, 2020). For an organization to experience significant growth and advancement, the members must share and accept the leadership's vision (Mui et al., 2018). In schools, student leaders are expected to manage all aspects of student life, whether they are academic or not (Murage et al., 2019). According to Ye et al. (2019), these performance expectations are entirely related to particular responses from the other side.

Leadership pressure is associated with various phenomena and conditions (Tonidandel et al., 2022). In context, during the pandemic, student leaders had to cope with the adjustments, meaning they were tasked to make decisions for the school quickly while also adapting to the ways of the pandemic in their personal lives (Dumulescu et al., 2021). Racial and cultural backgrounds also affect the pressure put upon student leaders; frankly, expectations from leaders differ depending on racial dynamics within an organization (Brooks et al., 2019). School culture or the support from the school as a whole is also indirectly entwined with the pressure a student leader has to handle (Liu et al., 2021). Connectively, student leaders may go through positive or negative experiences and challenges (Kouzes et al., 2018).

On the positive side, student leaders were generally able to develop and enhance leadership skills, such as interpersonal and problem-solving skills, which boosted their career prospects (Cui et al., 2022). Second, when they coordinate impactful movements that their fellow students value, they gain praise and appreciation, which stimulates their self-esteem, which transcends to personal confidence even after their time as leaders (Ketchen Lipson et al., 2019). Third, student leaders developed a sense of team orientation. They were able to connect groups, small or large, and lead groups to a better understanding of the ideas they discussed. Further, this encompasses having healthy relationships since many people support and believe in these leaders (Hensley et al., 2019).

On the contrary, the negative starts with how they were elected, wherein the position of a leader is usually seen as a reserved position and not as a worthy person, thus showing unhealthy leadership with the disbalance of elected-for and signed-up for the said position (Goodman, 2021). Second, the choice of leader in terms of gender, where men leaders are more appreciated and trusted than women leaders, leads to low self-esteem and a lack of confidence, especially for the belittled (Longman et al., 2018). Third, student leaders tend to find themselves physically drained after activities, leading to mental health problems that may deteriorate academic performance or even worsen the standard of living (Pereira et al., 2018).

Student leaders in the lens of academic and leadership pressure

Living in a contemporary society, developing traits and values will help individuals grow. In that case, leadership is one of the traits people should develop that can help them face society (Kuranchie et al., 2021). Further, leadership is an attribute that people might acquire at a young age. However, leading can be a burden for some student leaders since it can have an impact on both their well-being and learning ability. With the numerous projects and academic tasks student leaders handle, they might experience academic burnout and leadership pressure. Due to the highly dynamic environment's rapid evolution, the social environment in which we live is also changing quickly. According to research, today's youth experience constant anxiety in everything they do (Sharma, 2021).

According to the definition, stress is our body's response to events that might frighten or trigger people. It is also a process in which people try to comprehend and react to the struggles and challenges they might encounter (Alsohim et al., 2022). To relate, people experience stress in different aspects of their lives; it might be at school, home, work, and many more to mention. For students, academic stress is more prevalent and frequent.

Connectively, it is defined as the pressure students' experience whenever they encounter activities and work related to academics. There are both internal and external factors that can have an impact on a person's performance (Fuqiang et al., 2018). Moreover, it is also said that stress is one of the reasons that can affect students' motivation (Navales et al., 2021). As students encounter stress frequently, it becomes part of their lives. They developed expectations for their performance while setting their standards high at the same time (Thattil et al., 2018). Therefore, with the number of learners sharing their experiences regarding academic burnout, it is important to examine the factors that cause this phenomenon. Accordingly, school burnout is one of the factors contributing to academic pressure (Secer et al., 2019). The pressure that students face affects their lives negatively in different ways, such as academic performance, skills, mental state, physical state, and lifestyle (Parker et al., 2019). At the same time, based on research findings, it shows that anxiety is the most prevalent concern among student leaders in their experience; in numbers, it is 41.6% for all instances

(Thomas et al., 2019).

Student leaders may feel burdened by their roles, but at the same time, it also gives them a sense of purpose. However, time management and proper planning are the strategies the student leaders have to balance their academic and extracurricular activities (Ochangco, 2023). In essence, leadership is a difficult position, and student leadership is much more so. They must strike a balance between their leadership responsibilities and their academic obligations. Student leaders must have good mental health to manage their organizations and carry out their duties responsibly. Their ability to carry out their duties successfully depends on both their physical and mental health (Cantos et al., 2022).

Coping mechanisms of student leaders

Leaders are frequently under pressure. They must balance the demands of managing their academic work and leading organizations (APA, 2022). Student leaders employ many coping mechanisms to maintain their participation in their academic and extracurricular activities despite their responsibilities. People's lives can suffer severe negative effects from pressure and stress. Student leaders can typically handle the pressure given to them.

By definition, coping refers to proactive measures to alleviate undesirable emotions. Coping is the method used to manage stressful circumstances on both an internal and external level. Studies on academic stress have brought attention to the importance of coping mechanisms for mitigating outcomes. The extent to which people may combine various coping mechanisms and the adaptive effects of this have drawn increasing attention over time (Freire et al., 2020). In contrast to "defense mechanisms," which are adaptive subconscious or unconscious reactions that both work to reduce or tolerate stress, this phrase is used specifically to refer to the mobilization of voluntary and conscious acts. An effective support network and coping mechanisms will improve one's ability to manage stress and, in many cases, allow one to handle higher levels of stress (Algorani et al., 2022).

Stress levels can go up or down depending on coping mechanisms and behaviors. Coping mechanisms help individuals cope and lessen the impact of stressful situations. When people and students can manage pressure and stress, they perform at their best. Not all coping mechanisms work; many of them are unhealthy and worsen the situation for the student. Unfortunately, people frequently select unhealthy coping mechanisms over useful ones when confronted with stressful situations. In addition, when a crisis strikes, most people automatically choose inappropriate coping mechanisms, many of which may be harmful and have long-term effects that could endanger their lives and the lives of those around them. While switching our attention to something else during a crisis would be ideal, this is not always possible (Meadowglade, 2019).

Coping is the process of making cognitive and emotional adjustments to meet the demands of the environment, whether those demands are internal or external. In contrast to an aspect or a result, it is viewed as a mechanism. A small percentage of students quit school as a result of a challenging assignment. While some students choose healthy coping mechanisms like finding friends or getting involved in activities they enjoy, others choose unhealthy ones like fleeing or avoiding issues. Avoiding the problem, declining help from others, and abusing drugs are ineffective coping strategies. Because of this, some students, especially young people, think about self-harm and suicide (Vázquez, 2012; cited by Comendador, 2021).

Methodology

Research Design

The study uses a qualitative phenomenological strategy to investigate the experiences of the selected student leaders concerning leadership and academic pressure. Through semi-structured interviews, the researchers aim to examine the factors that contribute to leadership pressure and the participants' coping mechanisms. Purposive sampling is the sampling approach of the study. The research study has three student leaders that are part of the supreme student council (college) as respondents.

Participants

The interviewees of the research study are from Central Luzon State University (CLSU). The participants consist of three (3) student leaders from different organizations. The interview is conducted within the CLSU campus.

The study is at CLSU. The chosen school offers instruction for preschool, secondary, high school, senior high school, and college levels. The reason behind different organizations is to differentiate the work environment and support system.

Procedure

To gather data, the researchers conduct a semi-structured interview. The investigation utilizes an interview guide to ensure quick and effective data gathering. The interview guide contains 11 main questions, with an interview that may last a maximum of one hour. With a recording tool, the full response of each interviewee is recorded with their consent to remove any doubt as to the purpose of the data collection. Thematic analysis is the instrument employed to analyze the data and results of the study.

Ethical Considerations

As part of the ethical considerations of this study, the following are observed:

Informed Consent and Data Privacy Clause and Consent

The modified consent form provides participants all the information they need to make an informed decision about whether or not to take part in the study. Both the Data Privacy Clause and the Consent are presented at the outset of the survey.

Voluntary Participation

In accordance with what is stated on the consent form, participants have the freedom to join or withdraw from the study at any time without any penalty. Participation in this study is voluntary for those who are asked.

Confidentiality and Data Privacy Clause and Consent

Before being able to participate in the study, the participants must first sign a consent form. The researchers don't give out any of their findings to the public. To prevent individuals from being identified inside the data scientists collect, they mask their identities. Both the Data Privacy Clause and the Consent are presented at the outset of the interview.

Results Communication

Both plagiarism and research misconduct are not present in the study. The study adheres to all ethical standards and guidelines. The results shall be represented truthfully by the researchers.

Results and Discussion

This section shows the narrative of the participants, which is narrowed down into three themes on how they make meaning of leadership pressure from their personal experiences.

Leadership is developmental

The sub-themes under this section explain how leadership is not only a construct but also developmental—a process of growth and development. The participants recognized their lived experiences and values related to being a student leader. Their early responsibilities and upbringing are what make them the leaders they are today. As leaders, the main reason they're still striving for the position is their care for the public service. Meanwhile, several factors, including family, friends, and school advisers, are recognized as having contributed to their development. In addition, they also uphold values that they keep, which makes them the leaders they strive to be.

Early responsibilities

Student leaders are given obligations from a young age. They are exposed to duties and obligations from their homes or even at school as a result of several reasons. Their real-life encounters led them to be capable of handling responsibilities and leading others naturally. According to their account, their upbringing at home influences their development as leaders. Their independence started from their own experiences at home and became part of their lives. Additionally, their experiences from grade school are what made them start being leaders until now. For instance, P3 shared that ever since elementary school they have already started taking roles that require leadership.

"I already began to lead while I was in elementary school. In those days, the title "mayor" was still in use, so I'm already campaigning for positions like that. However, the level is still simple, and there are just little tasks to complete. However from that small tasks, it became my stepping stone to continue leading until now."

According to Mydin et al. (2019), the Social Change Theory Model of Leadership Development has been created to help students become more self-aware, develop leadership skills, and foster openness and accountability that will lead to constructive social transformation. The theory includes three values, and one of them is individual value. Wherein, the previous experiences of student leaders that they think contribute to their leadership skills today are part of their individual values. The self-assessment of individuals helped them gain some leadership knowledge and abilities. As a result, they felt more prepared to assume additional leadership responsibilities in student government.

Leader in nature

Through their different experiences, student leaders naturally develop leadership skills and instincts. It comes naturally to willingly serve people. According to their statements, they naturally developed an instinct to take leadership roles. At the same time, the influence of their family and peers played a role in their experience. Despite their hesitancy to take leadership roles, they have a self-urge to serve the people and the courage to lead them. For example, P2 stated that they were hesitating to take roles at first, but due to their peers, they continued taking leadership roles.

"At first, I was hesitant, but my friends pushed me to take on leadership roles because they thought I could do the job well. That's when I started taking on roles, and at the same time, they give me strength and motivation whenever I doubt my position. Hence, my friends are the ones who pushed me to be a leader."

Historically, the Great Man Theory explains how leaders are naturally born leaders (Posner, 2018). However, despite the experiences that made them the leaders they are today, every individual has a leader in them. It is the nature of people to be born leaders. Through the help of lived experiences, they can hone their leadership skills and influence their development.

Inspiration

During the interviews, the participants shared their inspirations and role models. In such a way, different people were mentioned. People from their past, like past teachers, are found to be an inspiration ever since to continue taking on the role of being a student leader. Meanwhile, they also take inspiration from themselves to continue to serve the people. For instance, P1 mentioned people from the Kabataan Party List, and martyrs of martial law were mentioned as role models or inspirations to move forward and lead the people.

“Maybe the Kabataan Party List is one of my role models or the party list that has the same agenda for the people. Their services and views for the people are aligned with ours, which means we’re not only serving the students per se but also the mass. Meanwhile, historically, I also admire martyrs of martial law, specifically Edgar Jopson, Lorena Barros, and many more.”

According to the conceptual study of Gross (2018), the researcher used Motivation to Lead as a conceptual framework. Whereas the findings revealed how student leaders' relationships and personal motivations drive them to succeed in their positions. Student leaders were able to serve and perform their duties effectively because of the support of various partnerships. Therefore, it contributes to their leadership development and growth as individuals.

Public service

All of the participants shared a common insight regarding the reason why they still strive for their remaining position. They strive to continue to stand up for the students and become the voice of the students to the higher-ups. At the same time, to rebuild or build a solid foundation for the council to pass it onto the next generation or term. In short, it is simply to serve the masses. P3 highlights how they continue to serve the people to inspire future generations to lead and serve the people.

“Gusto ko na makapag pasa din sa iba pang generation na makapag lead din sila ganon kasi maraming aspiring leader din talaga lahat tayo sarili natin namay leader within us. Kailangan lang ay may tao na parang magpupush o mag iinspire sayo o mag momotivate sayo para malabas yun so ayun lagi naming sinabi mga meetings namin and hopefully ngayong face to face marami na... makapag influence din ng ibang tao at makapag build ng new generation of leaders”

[The main reason why I still stick to being a leader is that I want to pass the torch to the next generation to lead the people. I believe all of us have leadership potential. We just need someone or something to motivate us to let the leader in us out. Hopefully, I can influence other people and build a new generation of leaders.]

According to Seidel et al. (2019), in a group setting, a servant leader tends to the needs of subordinates and inspires them to take on new duties. To explain further, being a student leader is not self-centered; it is about caring for other people more. With their natural instincts to serve the people, it became part of their lived experience that nurtured them as individuals and ideal leaders.

Core values

Participants defined the fundamental principles they uphold in their roles as student leaders. Another element in their growth and development is their commitment to these values. Respect was mentioned as one of the participants' main values. One of the fundamental virtues that everyone should possess is respect. Respecting other people's relationships and perspectives will keep the workplace organized and efficient. The other participant describes the values they value most as being passion and empathy. An essential component of understanding other people is taking an interest in their opinions. At the same time, they value doing work they are passionate about and that they enjoy. Meanwhile, P1 mentioned three core values they uphold and their council, which are genuine, militant, and patriotic. They believe a student leader must have a genuine agenda to serve the masses. While student leaders must be patriotic in some way, they should also know and understand the needs, rights, and welfare of the students. Lastly, a student leader must be militant. They should not be passive with the government, but they should be proactive and know when to act out the existing problems on campus.

“I will mention the core values that I and my party list uphold. Which are genuine, patriotic, and militant... Being genuine in what you do and your agenda to the masses is important... While being patriotic doesn't mean we should praise the government all the time and be passive toward them, Being patriotic means understanding the needs, rights, and welfare of the students and standing up for them. Militant might be a strong word, but I think student leaders should be militant. They should not be passive but know how to fight for the rights of their constituents despite the odds. I hope all of the student leaders have these three values, even if they're in different parties.”

A student leader should uphold some key values, according to Rejas et al., (2020). Empathy, sincerity, interaction, communication abilities, commitment, and initiative are among the values stated. The study emphasized the significance of these values and recommended that one should possess them in order to make a good leader. Being a student leader with strong principles is therefore an essential part of their growth. Every student leader has different fundamental values, but what makes them significant is how committed they are to them, which will support their development and leadership abilities.

Challenges under leadership pressure

The sub themes that fall under this section suggest that student leaders are constantly challenged by physical and mental struggles. These challenges are brought by excessive workload which come from the pressure of having to fulfill multiple responsibilities at once.

Academic struggles

Taking on leadership roles is a huge responsibility considering the amount of workload and tasks they handle, whether in their academics or organizations. Correspondingly, the participants revealed their challenges, including having trouble balancing their time. This results in poor academic performance as they feel pressured to handle the multiple tasks on their plate. Notably, they experience the burden affecting their academic performance during exam period, where events from their organization are also happening. In many instances, they have to sacrifice their own personal time or even their academics to give way to their organization. For instance, P1 stated that being a student leader while maintaining excellent academic performance is difficult, so it becomes a burden. They thus place more importance on their responsibilities as student leaders than on their academic performance. During exam season, they are particularly affected by the stress and burden, which rattle them.

"There are points... there are times when I really neglect it (pertaining to academics), but... I think it's okay? That's it, I don't think I'm super into... how about it?... like the... "into"? studying, like that."

According to Njaramba, L.W., et al. (2022), it can be inferred that academic pressure generates a negative relationship between leadership role demands and ethical leadership. The cumulative pressure to perform and the demands of their respective roles suggest a subsequent drop in morale and overall performance both in their roles and academia.

Affected performance and well-being

Essentially, the participants thought that having to take on leadership roles translated to troubles in their well-being and performance on both academic and leadership responsibilities. Moreover, with the pressure on having to attend to both responsibilities as well as the pressure on time management, the participants believed that such factors cause degradation in fulfilling their roles. Even moreso, the pressure of time and conflicting workload also affect their health and well-being.

"My time and mental health are affected ... I get overwhelmed easily, so when i do get pressured I wouldn't know what to do first, what I should do, what I should give time to."

While the effect of leaders on their constituents are usually given more importance, it is without doubt that leaders also experience lapses in their well-being and performance. Ultimately, active leaders usually feel the impact of leadership pressure more than passive leaders (Kaluzza et al., 2020). However, authentic leaders who experience affected performance and well-being tend to feed from these experiences to bounce back from the difficulties (Weiss et al., 2018).

Inability to handle multiple tasks

The participants agreed that balancing and handling the amount of tasks from their responsibilities in the academic and leadership realms have arguably become a burden. Furthermore, most of them said that the pressure on time with regards to having multiple tasks was ultimately felt during examination periods, whereas the pressure on performing well in the examination as well as the pressure to handle their constituents rattled them.

"Yes always, I always feel that. It doesn't go away but what you really need is to manage your time, your priorities. Of course our studies are our priority but since we have a sworn duty in our department you should manage it because they didn't force you to run, you took the initiative so you should manage your time."

The overloading of work is always a choice, and as student leaders, they approve of being subjected to more work, tasks and responsibilities. However, this also means they would have to face and conquer those challenges. Therefore, times may come where the conflicting workload may bring difficulties in holding up to all those responsibilities at once (Broker et al., 2018).

Decision-making

During the interviews, the participants shared their self doubt, self distrust and influence of pressure on decision-making. They think they are incompetent as leaders and lacking in self confidence due to the pressure and expectations. Pressure affects their decision making. However, they think that all of this is part of the process of being a leader.

"There is, but as much as possible we avoid it because it's not the healthy form of leadership that the students want and need. So it's necessary that everytime you're under pressure you need to be quick in making your decision."

Becoming a leader involves having to be a public icon. This means that a leader will always be watched, seen, and judged. Meanwhile, the decision making of people is influenced by social motivation, reward sensitivity, and distraction, which are all challenges faced by student leaders. With that being said, pressure and judgment would always meddle with their decision making (Ciranka & van den Bos, 2019).

Leadership pressure can be managed

This theme relates to how managing the demands of leadership necessitates constant interference and criticism. A student leader frequently has to handle two or more tasks at once, no matter how challenging they may be. According to the participants' responses, they often face difficulties with their duties as both leaders and students, which require them to manage stress and pressure. They have tackled a selection of coping strategies, including having emotional support, distractions, and time for self assessment.

Emotional support

Other people can provide leaders with emotional and moral support. May it be the members of their organization, their friends, or their family, having someone to lean on other than themselves could help with the burden they carry, alleviating some of the distress and pressure a leader experiences. By offering emotional support, you reassure, accept, encourage, and care for them, making them feel valued and significant. These people are the ones who cheer them up, encourage them, and sometimes give them needed advice. One participant stated that having the support of their peers makes them feel very courageous and outgoing.

"... Sometimes, when I don't have courage my friends say "We think you can do it," like that. They were the ones who pushed me to join."

According to Atoum & Al-Shoboul (2018), adolescents start to widen the circle of establishing social connections and seeking out others to share experiences with after childhood. In terms of security, help, and personal development, teenagers at this stage start to rely more and more on their friends. Family, friends, and teachers can influence a teen's emotional intelligence. Teenagers spend much time at home, hanging out with friends, and attending school. These sources frequently contact the person when experiencing personal, social, or emotional crises or situations.

Distractions

Distraction is the act of drawing someone's or a group's attention away from a particular area of interest to prevent or reduce the reception of a particular piece of information. Having time for leisure or distracting oneself if utilized properly can condition their mind to a more positive mental state. It provides a momentary escape—a break from the taxing responsibilities they have to do and to ease their anxiety.

"First of all, I'm watching something, do you know that... it's not a K-drama, on GMA... I'm looking forward to it when I arrive in the afternoon, maybe there will be a full episode, like that... the "Abot Kamay na Pangarap" and also the other one is Valorant."

Distractions can help us escape our daily schedules, jobs, stress, and anxiety. Psychologists have talked about how people divert their attention from unhealthy habits and discomfort by using distractions as a coping mechanism. Distractions serve as a helpful reminder that we are in charge of how we use our time and our minds (Catherine, 2019).

As a coping mechanism, the students similarly turn away from online learning. They spend their time interacting with those in their immediate circle. They also partake in recreational pursuits. When faced with stressful situations, students were more likely to use recreational skill approaches than physical or psychological coping mechanisms. These students typically take things slowly, are well-organized, and can take care of themselves when issues arise (Rotas & Cahapay, 2021).

Self-assessment

Self-assessment is the capacity to assess oneself to determine how much progress has been made. It is a skill that enables people to keep track of their performance or abilities, identify their areas of strength and weakness, and come up with appropriate self-diagnoses for problems. The goal of self-evaluation is to enable the person to understand the scope of his abilities and to enhance them without the assistance of a performance appraiser. It entails asking questions like, "What are my strengths?" and "What are the obstacles?" A participant said during the interview that they take criticisms and all positive and negative comments as motivation for themselves to improve their leadership skills.

"... First we hold a meeting, second we consult our adviser. So we'll tell them about what happened in the meeting then they will advise us on what needs to be done at the same time sharing their opinions. Third, we will plan on what to do next. Fourth is application, we will apply what we've talked about, then repeat the process. We also host team building to build the relationships among the team."

Self-assessment is looking at one's actions and output to make changes that improve performance and deepen learning. Self-assessment is most advantageous in terms of both achievement and self-regulated learning when used constructively and backed by training (Andrade, 2019).

Conclusion

Leadership is a developmental trait. Leaders tend to take on leadership roles at the early stages of their lives, hence, turning their loads of experiences, good or bad, into stepping stones to becoming successful leaders. Student leaders are resilient, adaptive, confident, and can bounce back from failure. With all those, they can sail through their endeavors and challenges by clinging to personal coping mechanisms. These challenges include the pressure on having to keep their performance up on academic and leadership tasks, having

to keep their body healthy despite loads of work, having to handle multiple conflicting tasks at once, and having to keep their minds settled in making decisions to steward their constituents. Breaking through, the participants in this study showed how coping mechanisms are purely personal and self-relational. They responded to the challenges primarily through their means, which resulted in differences in coping mechanisms. These coping mechanisms ranged from playing video games to seeing success in their projects.

In summary, given the personal observations and experiences related to student leadership and also the pertinent leadership pressure, the researchers found the significance of conducting a phenomenological study to grasp the notion among student leaders. In addition to advancing the body of knowledge in the area, the study's findings are supposed to increase public awareness of how leadership pressure affects the psychological well-being of student leaders.

Moreover, the researchers advise conducting further studies to add to the field of related knowledge. Similar research might be conducted in the workplace setting to provide a broad range of findings. Although the study focused on the experiences of student leaders, the researchers advise looking for more research on the other elements that affect the nature of leadership pressure. Age, position in the organization, and leadership capabilities are only a few limitations of the participants. To obtain viewpoints other than that of CLSU undergraduate students, the researchers advise future studies to include participants from any age and position in the organization other than the highest.

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